

Commentary on Zi 2026: Using the Integrated Aqua-Vegeticulture System for Effective Nutrient Recovery

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Abstract

The recent study by Zi et al. (2026) highlights the challenge of managing water quality in aquaponics while recovering nutrients from fish sludge, proposing a novel dual-loop aquaponic system (DLAS) as a solution. Zi et al. post that conventional single-loop systems cannot effectively process high organic loads without compromising water quality. This commentary presents evidence to the contrary, citing the Integrated Aqua-Vegeticulture System (iAVs), a single-loop model developed in the 1980s. Unlike the hydroponic units described by Zi et al., the iAVs utilizes porous sand biofilters that mechanically trap and biologically oxidize organic solids within the plant growth medium. This design facilitates in-situ mineralization of organic solids, demonstrating that single-loop systems can achieve high nutrient recovery rates without ammonia toxicity or the need for additional engineering. A re-examination of the iAVs methodology as a resource-efficient pathway toward integrated nutrient recovery is suggested.

Keywords: Integrated Aqua-Vegeticulture System (iAVs), Aquaponics, Sustainable Agriculture, Recirculating Aquaculture, Nutrient Recovery, Dual-Loop Aquaponics, sand filtration

1. Introduction

In their analysis of nutrient recovery efficiency, Zi et al. (2026) premised their Dual-Loop Aquaponic System (DLAS) on the assertion that "in single-loop aquaponic systems... nutrient-rich aquaculture sludge is typically mechanically filtered and removed from systems to prevent root clogging and maintain water quality" (p. 3). They conclude that single-loop systems face challenges in balancing pH, temperature, and nutrient concentrations when handling high organic loads.

While this observation holds true for most systems (e.g., Deep Water Culture or Nutrient Film Technique), it does not account for the capabilities of sand-based single-loop systems. This commentary asserts that the limitations described by Zi et al. are not inherent to single-loop designs but are specific to systems lacking adequate system design and filtration media for in-situ mineralization.

Attention is drawn to the Integrated Aqua-Vegeticulture System (iAVs), which addressed the issue of sludge retention and mineralization through a fundamentally different, yet simplified, approach

2. The Rationale for Single-Loop Sand Filtration

The iAVs is a closed-loop model developed at North Carolina State University (NCSU) in the 1980s (McMurtry et al., 1990a; Diver, 2006). Contrasting with the DLAS approach of isolating sludge in a side-stream Modified Biological Aerated Filter (MBAF), the iAVs directs 100% of the fish waste—both dissolved and solid—into the plant growing beds.

Zi et al. (2026) report that without their side-stream treatment, Mainstream SCOD and TAN levels increased significantly. However, historical data from NCSU demonstrates that sand biofilters can process total aquaculture effluent while maintaining water quality safe for fish, removing the requirement for the dual-loop separation proposed in the target study.

3. iAVs: System Architecture and Performance

3.1 Historical Origins and System Overview

The Integrated Aqua-Vegeticulture System (iAVs), developed and documented by Dr. Mark McMurtry, Dr. Douglas C. Sanders, and colleagues at North Carolina State University (NCSU) in the 1980s, is recognized as a foundational model for modern, sustainable aquaponics (Diver, 2006; Abdelrahman, 2018; Goddek et al., 2019). It is a closed-loop, integrated system that co-cultures fish and vegetables, designed to address waste accumulation challenges in recirculating aquaculture.

The development team integrated distinct specializations to address the complex biological interactions of the system, including horticulture and crop physiology (D.C. Sanders), plant mineral nutrition (P.V. Nelson), aquaculture and zoology (R.G. Hodson), and International Agricultural Development (H. Douglas Gross), agronomy (P.C. St. Amand), and plant pathology (J.D. Cure). Between 1984 and 1994, the iAVs project was supported by a comprehensive research consortium of 45 investigators and technical consultants. This multidisciplinary group held advanced degrees across diverse fields, including botanical nutrition, aquatic veterinary medicine, soil genesis, agricultural economics, and controlled environment engineering (including specialists from NASA and the Disney EPCOT Land Pavilion).

3.2 Mechanical and Biological Filtration Processes

The empirical results detailed in the works of McMurtry et al. (1987–1997) offer specific, quantifiable solutions and design parameters. In contrast to typical recirculating aquaculture systems that remove solid waste prior to water reuse, the iAVs method pumps raw, unfiltered fish tank effluent - containing both dissolved nutrients and suspended organic materials (solids) - directly from the bottom of the fish tank onto sand biofilters composed of medium-coarse sand (McMurtry et al., 1993a; 1993b; 1994; 1997a; 1997b). A specific builder's grade fractionation is used: predominantly Coarse (38.8%) and Very Coarse (33.3%) inert sand, with minimal silt/clay content (<1%) and negligible fine sand (<200 microns) (McMurtry et al., 1997).

To facilitate the removal of these solids from the aquaculture component, the bottom is sloped in a catenary shape to direct sediment toward the pump intake. These sand beds serve a triple function: providing a physical substrate for plant roots, acting as a medium for microbial nitrification, and facilitating the mechanical trapping and mineralization of organic waste solids on the sand surface (McMurtry et al., 1993b).

Once pumped to the biofilter, water is distributed via shallow irrigation furrows. These furrows act as sediment traps, slowing water velocity and allowing organic matter to settle on the sand surface (McMurtry et al., 1993a). Empirical analysis confirms that this "furrow effect" significantly increases Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) and concentrates essential elements within 50 mm of the furrow axis, providing a continuously renewed, localized supply of solid-phase minerals to the root zone (McMurtry et al., 1990).

To ensure complete drainage and prevent waterlogging or anaerobic zones, the bottom of the biofilter is constructed with a specific slope of 1:50 (2 cm drop per meter) toward the drainage outlet (McMurtry et al., 1997). As the filtered water drains from the sand bed, it cascades back into the fish tank, which re-oxygenates the water for the fish (McMurtry et al., 1990).

The system operates on a "reciprocating" (flood and drain) cycle, typically irrigating 8 times daily (McMurtry et al., 1997). Hybrid tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus* x *O. niloticus*) were utilized due to their rapid growth, high market value potential, and hardiness in intensive culture systems. The fish are fed at 08:00 (8 AM) and 13:00 (1 PM). The feed used in the original trials was specifically not fortified with vitamins or trace elements to avoid potential trace element toxicity (McMurtry et al., 1997).

3.3 Operational Parameters and Performance Attributes

The iAVs methodology exhibits specific operational characteristics regarding water chemistry and system maintenance, as documented in technical assessments by Dr. H. Douglas Gross (NCSU Department of Crop Science). Gross (1988) reported that iAVs facilities typically develop into functionally mature ecosystems within three months from initial startup. The longer the system is continuously operated without interruption or excess feed input rate, the more stable it will tend to become biologically and chemically (Gross, 1988).

A primary feature is inherent pH stability; the system naturally maintains a pH between 6.0 and 6.5, which is an optimal range for nutrient availability to most plants. This stability results from a biological balance where the acidifying process of nitrification is counteracted by the base-releasing effects of mineralization and plant anion uptake, removing the requirement for chemical pH adjusters often used in other hydroponic and aquaponic models (McMurtry et al., 1990a; McMurtry et al., 1997a). This stability, however, is contingent upon balancing nitrogen input with system assimilation (McMurtry 1989). Therefore, operators must strictly adhere to established design ratios regarding fish biomass and biofilter volume, while regulating feed inputs to match metabolic demand (McMurtry 1989; McMurtry et al., 1997). Adherence to these protocols ensures the ecosystem remains within the specific 6.4 (± 0.4) pH range subsequently identified as critical for optimizing soil ecology and plant nutrient availability.

Although prior knowledge of fish and plant care is beneficial for optimizing the biological balance, the system is designed for functional simplicity, allowing it to be operated by individuals with minimal technical expertise (McMurtry et al., 1997a). The design retains and mineralizes organic solids within the sand bed, ensuring sequestered nutrients are available for plant assimilation (McMurtry et al., 1993a). This integration of solids prevents nutrient deficiencies often associated with solids removal in other systems (McMurtry et al., 1994; Tyson 2011).

The ratio of plant growing area to fish volume is also critical. Specific biofilter-to-fish-tank ratios (ranging from 0.67:1 to 2.25:1) were established through empirical trials. Studies indicated that increased Biofilter Volume (BFV) resulted in improved water quality (lower TAN and NO_2^- concentrations) and increased fish growth rates (McMurtry et al., 1997). While vegetable yield per individual plant decreased with increasing BFV, the total fruit yield per plot (total area) increased significantly, suggesting that larger biofilters maximize total system biomass production (McMurtry et al., 1993b; McMurtry et al., 1997).

Extrapolation of annualized yield data by Professor Gross demonstrated that a unit with 3 m^3 water and 14 m^2 biofilter area could yield $\sim 150 \text{ kg}$ fish and over 1000 kg of vegetables annually, assuming a sub-tropical or controlled environment context (Gross, 1988; McMurtry et al., 1997b). Gross (1988) further highlighted the system's trophic efficiency, noting that every 1.0 kg of feed input yields approximately 0.75 kg of fish and 6.70 kg of vegetables.

Fig. 1. Original schematic of the iAVs method. Reproduced from McMurtry et al., (1990) with the purpose of critical comparison.

Fig. 2. Original schematic of the iAVs method. Reproduced from McMurtry et al., (1990) with the purpose of critical comparison.

4. Conclusion: A Call to Re-examine Established Methodologies

The research by Zi et al. (2026) provides valuable insights into the dynamics of nitrogen recovery and the specific microbial communities involved in sludge mineralization (e.g., *Cloacibacterium*, *Flectobacillus*). However, their conclusion that single-loop systems are inherently incapable of managing high organic loads requires qualification.

The foundational research of McMurtry et al. demonstrates that sand-based single-loop systems can effectively mineralize sludge in-situ. This commentary supports the consideration of the scientific community to consider sand-based filtration as a robust, simplified alternative to the multi-stage design of the DLAS.

Competing Interests

The author serves as a volunteer administrator for iavs.info, a non-commercial educational archive dedicated to preserving the historical scientific record of the Integrated Aqua-Vegeticulture System. This commentary received no external financial support, and the analysis is based exclusively on a review of peer-reviewed scientific literature.

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APPENDIX;

IAVS RESEARCH GROUP, NCSU

INVESTIGATORS AND CONSULTANTS (1984-1994)

Principle-Investigator

Name	Discipline(s)	From
Mark R. McMurtry, Ph.D.	Horticultural Science, Integrated Bio-production Systems, Environmental Design, International Development	1984

Co-Investigators

Name	Discipline(s)	From
Edward A. Estes, Ph.D.	Agricultural and Aquacultural Economics	1988
Blanche C. Haning, Ph.D.	Integrated Pest Management and Plant Pathology	1986

Name	Discipline(s)	From
Ronald G. Hodson, Ph.D.	Aquatic Ecosystems, Fisheries Management & Genetics	1986
Paul V. Nelson, Ph.D., FASHS	Botanical Mineral Nutrition & Greenhouse Management	1984
Robert P. Patterson, Ph.D., FCSSA	Agronomy, Soil Fertility, & Plant Physiology	1984
Douglas C. Sanders, Ph.D., FASHS	Horticultural Science and Plant Physiology	1986

Principle Consultants

Name	Discipline(s)	From
J. Lawrence Apple, Ph.D.	International Development, Plant Pathology	1985
Marc A. Buchanan, Ph.D.	Agricultural Ecology and Soil Science	1985
Stanley W. Buol, Ph.D.	Geomorphology, Mineralogy and Soil Genesis	1985
JoAnn Burkholder, Ph.D., FAAAS	Phycology and Aquatic Ecology	1988
James E. Easley, Ph.D.	Aquacultural Economics and Business	1987
Donald Huisingh, Ph.D.	Ecology and Environmental Resource Recovery	1984
Merle H. Jensen, Ph.D.	Agricultural Program Development (UAZ ERL)	1985
Thomas Losordo, Ph.D.	Recirculatory Aquaculture	1987
L. George Wilson, Ph.D., FASHS	Horticultural Science and Extension	1988

Ad Hoc Consultants (partial)

Name	Discipline(s)	From
Peter Cooke, Ph.D.	Intensive Aquaculture Systems (Disney World, EPCOT)	1986
Barry A. Costa-Pierce, Ph.D., FAAAS	International Aquaculture Development (ICLARM)	1988
Robert Jack Downs, Ph.D.	Controlled Environment Agricultural Research	1986
Kevin Fittsimmons, Ph.D.	Intensive and Recirculatory Aquaculture (ERL)	1986
H. Douglas Gross, Ph.D.	Crop Science and International Agric. Development	1987
Larry D. King, Ph.D.	Sustainable (Low-input) Agricultural Systems	1986
John Lavine, D.V.M.	Veterinary Medicine, <i>Cichlidae spp.</i> Specialist	1987
Michael Linker, Ph.D.	Entomology and Integrated Pest Management	1987
Steve Malvestuto, Ph.D.	Fisheries Assessment and Development	1988
George A. Marlowe, Ph.D.	Horticulture Research and Development (AVRDC)	1987
Robert H. Miller, Ph.D.	Soil Nutrition and Microbial Ecology	1987
Richard A. Neal, Ph.D.	International Aquaculture Development (USAID)	1986
Edward Noga, D.V.M.	Veterinary Medicine, Aquatic vertebrates	1988

Name	Discipline(s)	From
Glenn W. Patterson, Ph.D.	International Agro-Industries Development (ATI)	1988
Pedro A. Sanchez, Ph.D., FAAAS	Tropical Soils Management	1988
John C. Sager, Ph.D., FASABE	Controlled Environmental Life Support Systems (NASA)	1987
Ronald Sneed, Ph.D., FASABE	Agricultural Engineering, Irrigation Systems	1987
Kenneth Sorrenson, Ph.D.	Entomology and Greenhouse Pest Management	1987
Carolyn A. Williams, Ph.D.	Vegetable Horticulture and Physiology	1988

Other Technical Resources (partial)

Name	Field	From
Reed Altman, M.S.	Aquaculture Development (US Peace Corps)	1988
Ray Campbell, Ph.D.	Plant Nutrition and Tissue Analysis (NCDA)	1985
Dale E. Ettel, Ph.D.	Fish Feed Formulation (Purina Mills, Inc.)	1987
Vincent M. Foote, FIDSA	Integrated Systems Design	1984
Nancy Mingus, M.S.	Plant Tissue Analysis	1987
Boone M. Mora, D.V.M.	Commercial IAVS Demonstration project	1990
Brandy Noon, M.A.	Presentation and Graphics Design	1986

Name	Field	From
Stephen F. Pekkala, AIA	Architecture and Development Programming	1985
Martin L. Price, Ph.D.	Development Assistance and Networking (ECHO)	1988
Ray Tucker, Ph.D.	Soil Fertility and Analysis (NCDA)	1985